

Complexes of Lower Valent Rhenium

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In a previous communication¹, the analogy of nitroprusside ion with nitrosopentaacyano-rhenate(II) ion was demonstrated not only in its composition but also in its chemical reactions, such as, Gmelin's reaction and Legal reaction.

From polarographic reduction of nitroprusside, Kolthoff and Toren² concluded that the reduction took place in two stages, involving one-electron change in each case, as expressed in the following equations:

$[(\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{NO}))^{4-}]$ is probably Ungarelli's³ compound, prepared in 1925, which has been, however, contradicted by Cambi⁴ and proved to be $\text{Na}_4[(\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5)_2]$, $9\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

When nitroprusside analogue of rhenium¹ was subjected to polarographic reduction, only one wave, corresponding to one-electron change, was obtained. The reduction is reversible and the process may be explained as

I: 10^{-3} M- $\text{Na}_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]$ in 0.5 M- KNO_3
 II: ,, $\text{Na}_2[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]$ in ,, ,,

FIG. 1

The compound $\text{Na}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]$ has been described previously^{3,4}, but its composition is not certain. In case of rhenium, the existence of the compound $\text{Na}_3[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]$

1. Sen and Sarkar, *Science & Culture*, 1961, 27, 404.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 75, 1197.
3. *Gazzetta*, 1925, 55, 118.
4. *Atti Acad. Lincei*, 1926, 3, 8.

is expected in view of the stability of the well-characterised manganese analogues^{5,6}, $\text{Na}_3[\text{Mn}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]$. It has been prepared by passing pure and dry nitric oxide over sodium aquo-pentacyanorhenate(II) in absence of air at 130°. The properties of this compound are quite distinct from those of the nitroprusside analogue of rhenium. It does not show the characteristic violet colour with sulphide ion. It could not be reduced polarographically. Some of its reactions with different metal ions are recorded in Table I along with those produced by the manganese analogue.

TABLE I

Metal ions.	Character of precipitates with	
	$\text{Na}_3[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]$.	$\text{Na}_3[\text{Mn}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]$.
Ag^+	Yellow	Pale pink
Cu^{2+}	Red-brown	Brown-violet
Fe^{2+}	Green	Dirty brown
Fe^{3+}	Blue-green soln.	Deep green soln.
Co^{2+}	Green	Purple-brown
Ni^{2+}	Greenish yellow	Rose
Mn^{2+}	Pale yellow	Do
Zn^{2+}	Do	Blue-green

Nitrosopentacyanorhenate(II) reacts with alkali in a way similar to the nitroprusside, e.g.

The equilibrium reaction involving rhenium compounds was studied polarographically and the value of the equilibrium constant was found to be of the order of 10^{-4} ($\mu=0.5$), whereas in the case of nitroprusside a value of 10^{-4} was reported by Cambi and Szego⁶, which was recently redetermined by Kolthoff and Toren⁷ to be 10^{-6} ($\mu=0.5$). The rhenium analogue of nitroprusside appears to be at least hundred times more stable, vis-à-vis alkali, than nitroprusside. Details of the work will be published later.

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